

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN MODERN CLASSES

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Annotation This article explains unusual methods of foreign language teaching in education, modern trends in foreign language teaching, and a person-oriented approach to education as one of the main ways to achieve success in learning a foreign language.

Key words: innovative technology, simulation, methodology, foreign language, self-management.

Acceleration and modernization of education requires the introduction of such innovative technologies aimed at intellectually and emotionally creative education of a person. The principles of variability announced in the educational system allow higher education institutions to choose the model of the pedagogical process, including copyright. In such conditions, the foreign language teacher offers a certain freedom in choosing teaching models and technologies, without which the modern educational process cannot be imagined.

Innovative events create specific characteristics of the teacher’s activity in modern conditions, determine the transition from the paradigm of knowledge to interactive teaching methods. Traditional methods of teaching a foreign language involve the formation of knowledge in artificial situations, as a result of which future research does not see the connection of the studied subject with future professional activities. The most effective tool for developing the mindset of future graduates is simulation. This approach provides simulation of professional activity, its typical and important features. Its use allows the formation of communication skills and abilities;

development of the habit of independence and self-management, contributes to the real preparation of the student for future activities, helps to make lessons more lively, interesting and meaningful, allows the student to express his thoughts more and more often, it allows expressing feelings, thoughts, evaluation, that is, critical thinking.

Global integrative trends, expansion of intercultural interaction, and rapid social development contribute to mastering one or more foreign languages not only to communicate with representatives of other cultures but also to improve professional skills since modern society requires specialists to solve global issues. Teaching a foreign language has long gone beyond the boundaries of classrooms. The very term “distance learning of foreign languages” includes an entire educational paradigm related to the socio-cognitive, pragmatic, and ethical aspects of the foreign-speaking world.

In our country, new methods and requirements for teaching foreign languages in accordance with the European Framework Recommendations (CEFR) have been developed. It has created textbooks for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, the classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The need for learning foreign languages is also increasing day by day. Foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening and understanding) and each of them is given specific insights and skills.

The direct method of teaching, which is sometimes called the natural method, and is often (but not exclusively) used in teaching foreign languages, refrains from using the learners’ native language and uses only the target language. It was established in England around 1900 and contrasts with the grammar–translation method and other traditional approaches, as well as with C.J. Dodson’s bilingual method. It was adopted by key international language schools such as Berlitz and In lingual in the 1970s and many of the language departments of the Foreign Service Institute of the U.S. State Department in 2012.

The grammar–translation method is a method of teaching foreign languages derived from the classical (sometimes called traditional) method of teaching Greek and Latin. In grammar–translation classes, students learn grammatical rules and then apply those rules by translating sentences between the target language and the native language. Advanced students may be required to translate whole texts word-for-word. The method has two main goals: to enable students to read and translate literature written in the source language, and to further students’ general intellectual development. It originated from the practice of teaching Latin; in the early 1500s, students learned Latin for communication, but after the language died out it was studied purely as an academic discipline. When teachers started teaching other foreign languages in the 19th century, they used the same translation-based approach as had been used for teaching Latin. The method has been criticized for its shortcomings.

The audio-lingual method, Army Method, or New Key, is a style of teaching used in teaching foreign languages. It is based on behaviorist theory, which postulates that certain traits of living things, and in this case humans, could be trained through a system of reinforcement. The correct use of a trait would receive positive feedback while incorrect use of that trait would receive negative feedback. This approach to language learning was similar to another, earlier method called the direct method. Like the direct method, the audio-lingual method advised that students should be taught a language directly, without using the students' native language to explain new words or grammar in the target language. However, unlike the direct method, the audio-lingual method did not focus on teaching vocabulary. Rather, the teacher drilled students in the use of grammar.

The Silent Way. This is so called because the aim of the teacher is to say as little as possible in order that the learner can be in control of what he wants to say. No use is made of the mother tongue. Community Language Learning. In this method attempts are made to build strong personal links between the teacher and student so that there are no blocks to learning. There is much talk in the mother tongue which is translated by the teacher for repetition by the student. Immersion. This corresponds to a great

extent to the situation we have at our school. ESL students are immersed in the English language for the whole of the school day and expected to learn math, science, humanities etc. through the medium of the target language, English. Immigrant students who attend local schools find themselves in an immersion situation; for example refugee children from Bosnia attending German schools, or Puerto Ricans in American schools. .

Task-based language learning. The focus of the teaching is on the completion of a task which in itself is interesting to the learners. Learners use the language they already have to complete the task and there is little correction of errors.(This is the predominant method in middle school ESL teaching at Frankfurt International School. The tasks are subsumed in a major topic that is studied for a number of weeks. In the topic of ecology, for example, students are engaged in a number of tasks culminating in a poster presentation to the rest of the class. The tasks include reading, searching the internet, listening to taped material, selecting important vocabulary to teach other students etc.) The Natural Approach This approach, propounded by Professor S. Krashen, stresses the similarities between learning the first and second languages. There is no correction of mistakes. Learning takes place by the students being exposed to language that is comprehensible or made comprehensible to them.

All in all, The quality in the classroom is based on planning lessons and courses, understanding learners, managing this lesson, knowing the subject, managing resources, assessing learning, , taking responsibility for professional development, using inclusive practices, promoting today's skills and understanding educational policies and practice.

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